

Introduction to the Building Information Grammar – a Semantic Rich Shape Grammar

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a first approach of a Building Information Grammar (BIG) is presented and discussed. The current approach is adapted to build a corpus of building relevant information and further transport numerical analysis data, as well as encoded decoration occurrence and complementary information with a shape grammar. In this paper a first approach of this system is introduced by a case study presenting Late Period funerary monuments at Thebes (Egypt). BIG is based on two methodological concepts: Building Information Modeling (BIM) and description grammars. BIM is a process of modern building construction to manage semantic rich models (Borrmann *u. a.*, 2015) and includes methods to create and analyze spatial structures of buildings with additional semantic information. Used for ancient architecture and handled as a tool to analyze geometry and space relationships, it offers new possibilities for architectural heritage applications. The description grammar formalism transports complementary information with a shape grammar (Stiny und Gips, 1972). G. Stiny (1981) introduced the formalism to complement shape grammars for the description of designs. Description rules are linked to shape rules and work parallel and simultaneous. Descriptions describe the generated design in other ways, such as, terms of rooms, walls, windows, and other architectural components. So far metadata is passive in terms of completing and not directly influencing a shape grammar. With BIG, secondary data can be used actively to influence the design computed by the shape grammar, determine, and improve its quality. The shape grammar becomes an enriched grammar and a collection of information concerning the analyzed structures.

Keywords: Building Information Grammar, shape grammar, description grammar, Building Information Modelling, architectural analysis

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Introduction

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"Architecture is the learned game, correct and magnificent, of forms assembled in the light."

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(Le Corbusier)

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Architecture strikes a balance between creativity and practicality while serving both individual and social needs. Architectural structures are not just arrangements of bricks or stones but rather are an expression of the interplay between aesthetics, functionality, and construction technology. Additionally, in studying architecture in an ancient context also the cultural and historical conditions are relevant. In that sense architecture reflects cultural values, identities, and environments of the time it was built in.

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This paper presents a new methodological approach to enrich ancient architectural research in adapting and re-developing concepts from modern architectural design processes. So far there is no common method to relate building properties and the built structure. The presented approach combines two aspects of the computational design research field to build a semantic rich shape grammar. These aspects are Building Information Modeling (BIM) and description grammars. This method has the potential to offer hitherto unachieved and properly unexpected new insights into the way ancient architecture is studied, analyzed, and interpreted.

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This innovative new concept of architectural design analysis is presented with a case study of ten Egyptian Late Period funerary monuments. The linear substructures of the monumental rock-cut tombs from the Twenty-Fifth and Twenty-Sixth Dynasty include an open from above courtyard (CR), a niche entrance (NE), one or two halls (PH, H), eventually a sanctuary hall (SYH), and a sanctuary (SY) (**Error! Reference source not found.**,

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Figure 1). An example is shown for the tomb of Irtieru.

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Figure 1 - Ankh Hor (section), vertical alignment. Image: after Eigner (1984)

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The structures have been analyzed according to their accessibility, lighting system, decoration occurrence and distribution, and formal structure. These aspects are of primary relevance for the concept of an ancient Egyptian tomb design. The design and concept of ancient Egyptian funerary monuments were linked to religious motivated elements which are essential for ritual procedures, ceremonies, or religious believes. Ancient Egyptian veneration of the dead is based on two major concepts: continuing existence and immortality of the soul (Assmann, 1986). Physical continuation includes the mummification of the body, while social continuation is achieved through the memory of an individual. The personal identity and achievements of a deceased are eternalized pictorial and textual. The tomb functions as a link between physical and social continuation by keeping the body, informing the living about name and achievements, and serving as memorial place. Furthermore, the tomb is seen as house for the deceased's immortal soul (Assmann, 2010, 131-132) which lives in the tomb and communicates with the world of living. Furthermore, decoration in ancient Egyptian funerary monuments represents an important part of the monument's layout.

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Figure 1 - Model of Irteiru showing the main architectural components: 1. courtyard and niche entrance, 2. halls and 3. sanctuary

81 Aenean nec lorem. In porttitor. Donec laoreet nonummy augue. Suspendisse dui purus,
82 scelerisque at, vulputate vitae, pretium mattis, nunc. Mauris eget neque at sem venenatis eleifend.
83 Ut nonummy.
84

85 Research objectives, requirements, and innovative aspects

86 At the current stage of research any information that supplements an architectural design, such
87 as decoration position in room or spatial relations, must be consulted separately. With BIG this
88 process is simplified. It is an approach to combine analysis data with the developed shape
89 grammar to gather collected building information in the grammar. Building information are attached
90 to the shape grammar to present every gathered information of the analyzed structures. BIG can
91 transport information concerning the analyzed buildings as well as rules of dependencies and
92 intends to enlarge the shape grammar formalism. Beside analytic functions to analyze existing
93 designs BIG also works synthetic to produce new designs combining building information and
94 design production.

95 Building information are analysis data that include building relevant data and metadata. Design
96 production is given by a shape grammar to generate a set of design possibilities (design language).
97 The relationship between building information and design production will enable the search for a
98 best-fit-design based on analytic evidence. The process can be imagined as a design-circle.
99 Building information data gathered from architectural analysis provide sufficient information to
100 develop the grammar while the same building relevant data converge to create an enriched shape
101 grammar – the building information grammar (bottom-up approach).

102 Reversely, the output design can be analyzed according to the input components. If a complex'
103 design fits into the developed shape grammar and matches the proposed building information
104 functions, a best-fit-design can be searched by moving back and forth between the output design
105 and the input data (top-down-approach). That way metadata can actively influence a shape
106 grammar generated design, determine and improve its quality (**Figure 2**).

107

108 **Figure 2** - Concept of Building Information Grammar BIG

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110

110 Methodology

111 BIG is based on different concepts (**Figure 2**) concerning the analytical description of
112 architecture. These conceptual components include a shape grammar to provide shape specific

113 information and characteristics of the analyzed buildings, the concept of Building Information
114 Modeling (BIM) to provide and specify building related information, and descriptive grammar to
115 transport and display the additional building information synchronically with the shape grammar.
116 These components reveal a typological affiliation of the analyzed structures. This concept is based
117 on the assumption that ancient Egyptian funerary monuments followed an established language
118 of shape and meaning, specifically within a defined framework of time, location, status of the
119 owner, and degree of completion.

120 Shape grammars provide a formalism to analyze designs (analytical grammar) and to create
121 new designs (synthetic grammar). A shape grammar consists of a collection of forms, symbols,
122 and shape rules to define a shape language generated by the grammar (Stiny, 2006, 228-260).
123 Shapes derive from an initial shape by applying the defined shape rules (Knight und Stiny, 2015).
124 A shape rule initially says that a shape in a design in any orientation of any size, can be replaced
125 by another shape, according to the rule. If no other rule in the grammar can be applied, the process
126 is terminated (Stiny und Gips, 1972).

127 G. Stiny presented a formalism for the description of designs (Stiny, 1981). The description
128 rules are linked to the shape rules and work simultaneously. While the shape grammar describes
129 the spatial composition of designs the descriptions describe the designs in other terms.
130 Consequently, each shape rule has a corresponding description rule. BIM is a process of modern
131 building construction to manage and record semantic rich digital models (Borrmann *u. a.*, 2015). It
132 provides an immediate availability of all relevant data, improved information exchange, and
133 continuous data processing.

134 In a recent dissertation project (in reviewing process) ten monumental rock-cut substructures
135 of Late Period funerary complexes at Thebes have been analyzed according to their architectural
136 properties, including spatial analysis (Wutte, Ferschin und Suter, 2015) and decoration occurrence
137 and distribution (Wutte, 2018), as well as their design formalism through an analytical shape
138 grammar (Wutte und Duarte, 2021).

139 The shape grammar (design production) as well as analysis data (building information) are used
140 to build the building information grammar (BIG). The tomb of Irtieru is exemplary presented in this
141 paper.

142 The detailed data has to be worked out individually depending on the analyzed structures. For the
143 current paper, the following components are available:

144 Shape grammar **Error! Reference source not found.** presents an example of a shape rule
145 from the shape grammar of Late period funerary monuments at Thebes (Wutte und Duarte, 2021).
146 The rule specifies that a small space f_2 is added to a larger space f_1 along a straight main axis.
147 Additionally, to some extent, the shape grammar, developed in previous research is transporting
148 building information, such as room functions and conditions (Wutte und Duarte, 2021). Functional
149 information computations run parallel to a shape grammar and are classified as functional
150 conditions (Stiny, 1981). Functional elements are related to the application of shape rules in the
151 grammar. Beside their conditional behavior they provide insights into room function characteristics.
152 Conditions and functional conditions of the shape rule in **Figure 3** specify under which conditions
153 the rule can be applied. Functional conditions control which room functions are dedicated to f_1 and
154 f_2 .
155

Shape rule

conditions

functional condition

3 Adding a small space

$L \in \{L_{cr}, L_{ph}, L_h, L_{syh}\}$
 $W \in \{W_{cr}, W_{ph}, W_h, W_{syh}\}$

$L_1 \in \{L_{ne}, L_p, L_{sv}, L_{an}\}$
 $W_1 \in \{W_{ne}, W_p, W_{sv}, W_{an}\}$

$W_{s2} > W_{s1} > W_{s2}$

if $f_2 = NE \Rightarrow L_1 = W_1$

$f_1 \in \{CR, PH, H, SYH, AC, NE\}$
 $f_2 \in \{NE, P, SY, CO, SC, RP, AN\}$

if $f_1 = CR \Rightarrow f_2 \in \{NE, P, AN\}$

if $f_1 \in \{H, PH, SYH\} \Rightarrow f_2 = SY$

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157 **Figure 3** - Example of a shape rule to add a small space from the shape grammar
 158 of Late period funerary monuments at Thebes (Wutte und Duarte, 2021)

159

160 Building Information Data

161 Data concerning natural lighting conditions

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163 Categories for specifying natural lighting conditions include direct daylight, indirect daylight,
 164 and no daylight. Starting from a source of natural light such as an opening, an open courtyard or
 165 an open door, the intensity is calculated and weighted by representing the path length (distance)
 166 from source to space. If a space is directly lit, the path length from source to space is 2. Indirect
 167 lighting is represented by 4, 6, or 8, while unlit spaces are identified with ∞ (Wutte, Fersch und
 168 Suter, 2015). In each monument, rock-cut spaces receive daylight through the open from above
 169 courtyard. No space other than the courtyard has access to direct daylight. Consequently, mainly
 170 the courtyard and niche entrance, as well as entrance areas had been lit (Figure 4).

171

172 **Figure 4** - Natural lighting conditions in the rock-cut structure of Pabasa
173 representing the situation of a door installed and closed behind the courtyard.
174 Intensity ranges from 2 (direct light) to ∞ (no light)
175

176 *Data concerning accessibility of rooms*

177
178 Due to the linear structure of the monuments, spaces are aligned on a straight main axis and

179 optional side axes (

180 Figure 1). Archaeological data (Eigner, 1984, 87) suggest that the rock-cut rooms have been
181 closed after burial. This in turn suggests that the rooms behind the niche were not
182 accessible to visitors. Primary room functions include two sections: *offering cult* (including mortuary
183 cult) and *funerary cult* (including actions during funeral). In this paper the terms offering cult and
184 funerary cult were chosen to represent different parts of the tomb conducting different religious
185 aspects and consequently with different degrees of accessibility. The term *offering cult* is used for
186 parts which are at least semi-public. Semi-public means that, for example, relatives of the
187 deceased were able to access and offer goods to the immortal soul. For these sacrifices, offering
188 plates and false doors are located at an accessible place. Offering cult includes mortuary rites and
189 concerns continuing offerings to the deceased after his death (Eigner, 1984). The term *funerary*
190 *cult* includes in general Osiris cult rites (Shaw, 2004) and any aspect of ceremonial rites during the
191 funeral (Hays, 2010). This part of the tomb was closable and most likely only accessible for specific
192 personnel, such as priests, to perform specific rites. This classification implies a distinction
193 between offering cult and funerary cult. The differentiation is specified by several aspects (Figure
194 5):

195 *Spatial separation* – the funerary cult area was most probably closed and sealed (Eigner,
196 1984). According to Eigner separations are verifiable at the entrances to first halls.

197 *Spatial effect* – The spatial appearance of tomb areas is in stark contrast. Considered issues
198 for this effect are lit versus unlit rooms or open and wide versus compact and cavernous rooms.
199 These are aspects which result in a difference of room appearance.

200 *Decoration program* – Additionally, the decoration program defines a differentiation between
201 the areas which show scenes and texts describing life and biography of the deceased versus
202 scenes and texts pertaining the journey to the underworld, regeneration, and afterlife.

203 *Offering places* – The structures include offering places of different kinds, such as offering
204 tables, shrines, altars, and false doors in the courtyard (secondary offering places) and a false
205 door or statue shrine as sanctuary and main cult destination. This allocation is comparable with a

206 temple, where the main cult destination is only accessible for the pontifex maximus (pharaoh) or
 207 his representatives (priests). Secondary offering places are also accessible for other individuals.
 208 Accessibility information differentiates between accessible (AB+) and inaccessible (AB-).
 209

210

211 **Figure 5 - Results of the Natural lighting and Pedestrian circulation analysis**
 212

213

213 *Data concerning decoration elements*

214

215 To study decoration of Late Perion funerary monuments, decoration data has been digitized
 216 and referred to space in a five-step workflow.

217

- 217 1. Data gathering from publications and categorization of decoration scenes and texts in a
 218 database.
- 219 2. Referencing decoration in space.
- 220 3. Creation of a taxonomic hierarchy (ontology) of classes, categories and subcategories.
- 221 4. Spatially integrated visualization representing the decoration in space.

222

222 Space patterns¹ (Wutte, Ferschin und Suter, 2015) illustrate decorations in relation to spatial
 223 properties, room-decoration adjacencies, room function, and room scale (Figure 9).

224

- 224 5. Diagram visualization for quantitative analysis. Occurrence and distribution of scenes are
 225 illustrated in charts using R ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016) (Figure 8).

226

227 Consequently, decoration data gathered from numerous publications and excavation reports
 228 are available in an easy to manage database (Figure 6) and are space-referenced (Figure 7)². This
 229 information can be further processed in BIG as decoration input data. For this paper the following
 230 decoration categories have been considered: DLifeSce - Daily Life Scenes, Own - Owner, God -
 231 God, OffSce - Offering Scene, FunSce - Funerary Scene, Txt - Text, St - Statue, GeoPatt -
 232 Geometric Pattern, ArchDec - Architectural Decoration.

¹ <http://spacepatterns.com/wp/about/>

² The entire data will be published as PhD thesis. For the current paper merely a relevant excerpt of this data is given.

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Figure 6 - Distribution of occurring subcategory scenes in Irtieru, including scene preservation information and location

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Figure 7 - Space-referenced decoration classes: distribution of scene (Sce) and text (Txt) over the rock-cut structure of the tomb of Irtieru

Results

243 A detailed example is given in (Table 1). Rule 3 of the shape grammar developed in Wutte,
 244 Duarte (2021) to add a small space is accompanied by additional building information
 245 dependencies. Dependencies include the beforenamed data about natural lighting intensity,
 246 accessibility, and decoration. Natural lighting and accessibility data reflect the situation of a closed
 247 rock-cut part as it is suggested by Eigner (1984, 87). In this scenario a door, most probably sealed
 248 at the time of the funerary, regulates the access of the rooms behind the niche entrance. In the
 249 tomb of Pabasa no niche entrance is included. Consequently, the door was closing the area behind
 250 the courtyard.

- 251 - In the grammar a space's access to light is specified as NL 2, NL 4, NL 6, NL 8, or NL ∞
 252 representing the intensity of natural daylight
- 253 - Accessible areas are defined as AB + while inaccessible rooms are specified by AB -
- 254 - For every space that can be generated according to rule 3 the dedicated decoration is
 255 specified

256 The information listed in table 1 is based on data emerged from beforementioned analysis.
 257 Figure 10 shows an exemplary computation of rule 3. In the derivation of the tomb of Irtieru a niche
 258 entrance as small space is added to the courtyard. According to the building information conditions
 259 the courtyard (CR) is directly lit (value 2), while the niche entrance (NE) is lit with a light intensity
 260 of 4. The niche entrance is open from one side but closed from above. It is connected to the
 261 courtyard with an opening and was not closeable with a door. The courtyard as well as the niche
 262 entrance are accessible. These spaces were used for offerings and representation of the tomb
 263 owner. The courtyard was not decorated. Archaeological evidence suggests that the courtyard
 264 remained unfinished (*South Asasif Conservation Project, Irtieru, 2020*). The niche entrance is
 265 decorated with scenes of offerings, owner, and god and contains architectural decorations such
 266 as a doorframe and a cavetto cornice (Figure 6; *South Asasif Conservation Project, Irtieru, 2020*).
 267 In the example of Figure 10 the courtyard is outlined without possible side naves and pillars. This
 268 is because the side naves are built in later stages of the grammar. Also, some tombs have not
 269 had side naves and pillars. This is considered in the example of table 1 and fig. 10. Only decoration
 270 located at the appearing walls of the courtyard which is built with rule 3 are included. Consequently,
 271 decoration located at walls of the courtyard's side naves or courtyard's pillars are not included at
 272 this stage.

273

274

Figure 8 - Exemplary computation of Rule 3 from the derivation of the tomb of Irtieru

Table 1 - Example of the operating principle of BIG: Shape rule 3 (Wutte und Duarte, 2021) to add a small space with additional building information dependencies concerning natural lighting, accessibility and decoration

shape rule

3 Adding a small space

natural light

- if $f_1 = CR \Rightarrow NL 2$
- if $f_1 = PH \Rightarrow NL \infty$
- if $f_1 = H \Rightarrow NL \infty$
- if $f_1 = SYH \Rightarrow NL \infty$
- if $f_1 = AC \Rightarrow NL \infty$

- if $f_1 = CR \Rightarrow f_2 = NE, P \Rightarrow NL 4$
- if $f_1 = NE \Rightarrow f_2 = P \Rightarrow NL 6$

- if $f_2 = NE \Rightarrow NL 4$
- if $f_2 = SY \Rightarrow NL \infty$
- if $f_2 = CO \Rightarrow NL \infty$
- if $f_2 = SC \Rightarrow NL 2$
- if $f_2 = RP \Rightarrow NL 2$
- if $f_2 = AN \Rightarrow NL 4$

accessibility

- if $f_1 = CR \Rightarrow AB +$
- if $f_1 = NE \Rightarrow AB +$
- if $f_1 = PH \Rightarrow AB -$
- if $f_1 = H \Rightarrow AB -$
- if $f_1 = SYH \Rightarrow AB -$
- if $f_1 = AC \Rightarrow AB -$

- if $f_1 = CR \Rightarrow f_2 = P \in AB +$
- if $f_1 = NE \Rightarrow f_2 = P \in AB +$

- if $f_2 = NE \Rightarrow AB +$
- if $f_2 = SY \Rightarrow AB -$
- if $f_2 = CO \Rightarrow AB -$
- if $f_2 = SC \Rightarrow AB +$
- if $f_2 = RP \Rightarrow AB +$
- if $f_2 = AN \Rightarrow AB +$

decoration

- if $CR \Rightarrow d \in \{DLifeSce, OffSce, Own, ArchDec, Txt (BkOfDd, RitDy, RitNt, Bio, FunTxt), St, God, \emptyset\}$
- if $NE \Rightarrow d \in \{OffSce, Own, GeoPatt, ArchDec, Txt (FunTxt, Tit, PyrTxt), God, \emptyset\}$
- if $PH \Rightarrow d \in \{OffSce, Own, ArchDec, Txt (BkOfDd, RitDy, RitNt, PyrTxt, FunTxt, OffTxt, Bio, CoffTxt), St, God, FunSce, \emptyset\}$
- if $H \Rightarrow d \in \{Txt (BkOfDd, PyrTxt, OffTxt, FunTxt), \emptyset\}$
- if $SYH \Rightarrow d \in \{Own, ArchDec, Txt (PyrTxt, FunTxt), St, God, \emptyset\}$
- if $SY \Rightarrow d \in \{ArchDec, St, God, \emptyset\}$
- if $CO \Rightarrow d \in \{Own, ArchDec, Txt (FunTxt), St, \emptyset\}$

if EN \Rightarrow $d \in \{\text{DLifeSce, OffSce, Own, Txt (FunTxt), ArchDec, } \emptyset\}$

Discussion and conclusion

Using shape grammars to describe the formal structure of architecture is a systematic and detailed way to analyze architectural structures. Analytical grammars are a promising approach to examine and better understand ancient built structures. Nevertheless, it lacks descriptions of other kind than forms - this is where BIG comes in. As an addition to the shape grammar, BIG transports further information about a complex structure and building related properties. This information can be of various nature, such as lighting conditions in rooms, accessibility of rooms, or decoration occurrence in rooms. The relevance of the metadata depends on the building's context. In case of ancient Egyptian funerary monuments, the beforenamed information are of importance because they further describe the function of the building's areas. Furthermore, BIG builds a corpus of building relevant information and correlates analysis data and built structure.

In summary, BIG provides:

- a semantic rich shape grammar to transport building related information
- a corpus of building relevant information
- search function to generate the best-fit-design for existing tombs, reconstructed unfinished tombs, extended tombs according to the rules and probability, or unknown tombs

295

The exemplary tomb of Irtieru (Figure 8) was left unfinished as was the decoration of its substructure. Information about lighting intensity and accessibility of the courtyard (CR) and niche entrance (NE) are as expected and fulfill the building information dependencies specified for courtyards and niche entrances. Figure 8 shows that the courtyard's decoration information remains empty because the courtyard in the tomb of Irtieru was undecorated. Anyway, BIG suggests a variety of scenes and texts for the courtyard considering other tombs in the analyzed corpus. Hence, the courtyard of Irtieru does not represent the best-fit-design. Since the present shape grammar does not allow the replacement of the courtyard, a suggested change in the design is not possible under the given conditions. The niche entrance contains remains of offering scenes, owner scenes, god scenes, and geometric patterns as well as architectural decorations. Although, there are fewer remains than in other niche entrances, the decorative program is representative for those entrances.

308

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